

Startup IT Solutions Journey from an Idea to Market

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Running a StartUp is a tough job, you need to put in long hours of work and undeterred energy to make even a small dent in the market. This means donning multiple hats – finding, hiring and handling talent, developing and marketing your products while at the same time raise funds. Here's how Startup IT solutions could help you.

Startup consulting services would help you manage and run a structured business that has a fail fast approach thereby increasing your profits and monitoring the expense. Choosing the appropriate IT partner or entering into a strategic partnership to co-create and co-invest in a novel idea would help you manage the show in an organized manner.

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Conceptualization – Build a strong business case

Startup consulting services would help you build a strong business case for your idea. They would be able to pin-point areas of improvement and come up with innovative ideas to implement the concept. Your partner company would be able to fetch you all the numbers in terms of market research, end-user analysis and trend analysis. It is also worthwhile to assess similar products in the market and run a gap analysis. After a thorough study, you can define the technology deployment scenarios after brainstorming the pros and cons. During this stage your startup consulting solution should have a detailed roadmap ready for the product/service you wish to deliver.

Proof of Concept and Prototype – Prep for venture capitalists

The next most important milestone to kicking off your start up is to raise funds. You would have to create a Proof of Concept (PoC) and Prototype for your idea to draw investors and explain the profit potential and scalability of your project. Startup development services from your IT partner would help you to put-together a fool proof PoC that help investors understand the product, its USPs, risks, potentials and how much of a game changer the product is. There are cases where the IT partner co-invests with the startup at this stage.

Marketing activities – Pre and Post Launch

Does your business startup consultant provide digital marketing services? You have to define a marketing strategy that is in-line with the sales activities of your project. Work on creating compelling creative marketing assets such as landing pages, blogs, emails, PRs, etc. Also device effective digital marketing techniques to put your product out there in front of the right kind of audience.

Architecture Design and Development –Leverage technology trends

A competent StartUp IT solutions provider would have professionals who are well-versed with the various technologies and technology stacks that are trending today. They would be user experience experts who are capable of defining the best architecture

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design – database architecture, Technical architecture and deployment architecture design for the project. After this stage the actual development takes place. Once the development modules have been defined a phase-wise release of the developed product takes place. All this is done with an aim to foster faster development, lesser defects and lesser expenses.

A focus on faster go-to-market – Quicker returns

Startup It solution providers would be able to define a suitable product transformation methodology that focus on faster go-to-market time. They would be able to provide standardized service packages that are crucial to keeping your project affordable. This can be accomplished by identifying and defining MVPs (Minimum variable product) for your project. MVPs alongside other tools that facilitate adaptability, flexibility and scalability will help get your product successfully to the markets.

Deployment and Testing – Error free implementation

Your startup development partner would be able provide Quality assurance and testing services to ensure that the product is deployed efficiently and remains bug-free throughout. The various testing services include the following but are not limited to the same.

- Test case documentation
- Functionality testing
- Plan testing Strategy
- Usability Testing
- Compliance testing

Transition of your product from the testing environment into production can be tricky. Competent StartUp development services would be able to ensure a smooth transition and proper functioning of the product. This is accomplished by running user scenarios, conference room pilot and parallel runs.

Support and maintenance – Reliable solutions

Once the product has been rolled out, you would have to maintain a team to monitor and provide support for the same. IT vendor partner can help by taking up this

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responsibility as it would work out to be expensive to maintain a large in-house team for the same purpose.

Every StartUp works at its own pace and set guidelines, hence it is essential to define the extent and type of engagement that you expect from your business StartUp consultant. You will have to choose a partner who is flexible to match your requirements and work together to successfully deliver the product.

Gateway Technolabs has been a contributor to IT automation and other [IT consultancy services in Germany](#) for quite some time now. We have a prominent presence in Germany and the Nordic region and hence we are very familiar with the market there. Our experience can be mapped by the fact that we have successfully provided IT partnership solutions to over 25 startups and are still counting. To know more about our StartUp consulting services click here.

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